

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF POPULATION MIGRATION

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the analysis of data on population migration - the movement of people (migrants) across the borders of a territory (country, region, district, etc.), associated with a change in place of residence (stay), internal migration - intrastate migration - the process of population movement within the country, and external migration or international migration - territorial movement of population between different countries.

Keywords: migrant, migration, population migration, internal migration, external migration.

Population migration data is an integral part of national demographic statistics. Population migration affects the dynamics of the population size, alters its demographic characteristics, and changes its national composition.

Population migration is the movement of people (migrants) across the borders of a territory (country, region, district, etc.) associated with a change in place of residence (stay). Every movement related to migration expresses two events: departure - the area (departure region) the migrant leaves, and arrival - the area (arrival region) where they arrive.

People's territorial movement can occur both within a country and between countries. Therefore, migration is divided into interstate and intrastate. The former is usually called external (international) migration, and the latter is internal migration.

To describe the volume of migration during a specific period (usually one year), data on the absolute number of arrivals and departures is used. The difference between them for a specific territory during a specific period indicates the migration increase of the population.

In many Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) countries, the formation of current records related to migration associated with a change of permanent residence is carried out by processing statistics on arrivals and departures obtained from the internal affairs bodies (forms) at the time of registration and deregistration (at the place of residence). Based on the same principle, migration flows between countries are statistically monitored in most CIS states. In Armenia and Moldova, migration data is taken from the population registers by statistical authorities.

Here we will place a link to the annex - a table prepared for the meeting in Chişinău.

The statistical registration form for departure (departure) typically includes the following details about the migrant: date and place of birth, gender, nationality, place of residence (registered address), origin, when they arrived, how long they have been living in the place, purpose of arrival, workplace, marital status, whether they arrived with a spouse, and information about children aged 16 (15, 14) or younger traveling with adults.

The concept of migrant numbers involves a certain conditionality, as one person may change their place of residence multiple times within a year.

The number of arrivals refers to the absolute number of persons who have entered a specific territory from outside of it.

The number of departures refers to the absolute number of persons who have left a specific territory for beyond its borders.

Statistical data processing on migration allows for the collection of information on migrants grouped by territorial and various socio-demographic

characteristics (such as gender, age, ethnicity, marital status, education level, etc.).

Migration growth (migration balance) is the difference between the number of people who arrived in a certain region and the number of people who left it during a specific period. Migration growth can be positive (if the number of arrivals exceeds the number of departures) or negative (if the number of arrivals is less than the number of departures).

Internal migration refers to the movement of people within a country. These migrations do not cross the country's borders. Citizens of a specific country participate in internal migration. Internal migration affects the territorial distribution of the population within the country without influencing the total population size.

External migration or international migration refers to the territorial movement of the population between different countries. An **international migrant** is any person who changes their permanent place of residence.

For external migration, the terms "emigration" and "immigration" are used.

Emigrant number refers to the absolute number of people who leave the country for permanent or temporary residence in another country.

Immigrant number refers to the absolute number of people who enter the country for permanent or temporary residence.

The classification of a person as an emigrant or immigrant is carried out according to the legislation of each country (based on time, purpose of departure/arrival, and other factors).

Typically, the number of emigrants includes those who have left the country for permanent residence, while the number of immigrants includes those who have entered the country for permanent residence.

External migration balance is the difference between the number of immigrants and the number of emigrants in a given region over a specific period. If

the number of immigrants exceeds the number of emigrants, the external migration balance is positive; otherwise, it is negative.

The CIS Statistics Committee obtains migration data related to changes in permanent residence each year from the national statistical services of member states, based on questionnaires approved by the Council of Heads of Statistical Services of the CIS. These data are exchanged within the framework of interstate information exchange.

Data on migrants is provided annually:

The number of people who have arrived and departed for permanent residence, the countries of departure/arrival, gender, and age groups, including the 15-29 age group;

The total number of internal migrants, classified by gender and major age groups;

The number of international and internal migrants classified by gender and five age groups (age groups differentiated as below working age, working age, above working age, and youth aged 15-29);

The education level of incoming international migrants;

The purpose of the arrival of international migrants (with major purposes specified - work, study).

Quarterly data on arrivals, departures, and migration growth is provided.

The International Organization for Migration (IOM) was established in 1951 as an intergovernmental organization. The work of the IOM is based on the principle that humane and orderly migration should benefit both migrants and host societies. The IOM, together with its partners, carries out activities aimed at assisting in solving operational problems in the field of migration; raising awareness of migration issues; supporting social and economic development through migration; and making every effort to ensure that the human dignity of migrants is fully respected and that they are well-off.

In 2016, the United Nations and the IOM signed a Relationship Agreement (A/70/976). The IOM is the coordinator of the UN Migration Network, established by the Secretary-General in 2018.

According to the latest ILO Strategic Plan, the organization's three main goals for 2024-2028 are: saving lives and protecting people on the move, finding solutions to displacement and facilitating regular migration pathways.

Migration data

According to the latest estimates from the Population Division, the number of international migrants in the world, i.e. people living outside their country, is 281 million. Migrant women account for 48 per cent of international migrants. Almost three-quarters of international migrants are between the ages of 20 and 64, and 41 million international migrants are under 20. The largest numbers of international migrants reside in Asia and Europe (31 per cent each), North America (21 per cent), Africa (9 per cent), Latin America and the Caribbean (5 per cent) and Oceania (3 per cent).

As migration data is collected by a variety of organizations and institutions, it is difficult to provide a clear picture of migration. The ILO's Global Migration Data Analysis Centre maintains the Global Migration Data Portal, which serves as a unique source of comprehensive and up-to-date information on the subject. This website brings together data from a variety of sources to provide a snapshot of the migration situation for government officials, national statistical offices, journalists and the general public.

According to the ILO's Missing Migrants Project,

61,867 migrant deaths have been recorded worldwide since 2014. The deadliest migration route is the central Mediterranean route, where at least 22,871 people have died. And the deadliest land route is the US-Mexico border crossing.

Global efforts

Migration is global in nature, requiring global approaches and global solutions. On 19 September 2016, the UN General Assembly convened a high-level meeting to present the report of the UN Secretary-General on “In safety and dignity: addressing the great movements of refugees and migrants”.

Heads of State and High Representatives unanimously adopted the main outcome document, the New York Declaration for Refugees and Migrants, which expresses the political will of world leaders to save lives, protect human rights and fairly share responsibilities at the global level.

In December 2018, UN Member States adopted the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration at the Intergovernmental Conference on International Migration in Marrakech, Morocco.

In May 2022, at the first International Forum on Migration, the General Assembly adopted a Progress Declaration to review progress in the implementation of the GCM and provide a roadmap for enhanced global cooperation on migration.

In the New York Declaration for Refugees and Migrants, adopted in September 2016, the General Assembly decided to develop a global compact for safe, orderly and regular migration. The compact offers a unique opportunity to improve migration governance, respond to contemporary migration challenges and enhance the contribution of migrants to sustainable development.

International Migrants Day

On 4 December 2000, the General Assembly proclaimed 18 December as International Migrants Day (resolution 55/93). On this day in 1990, the Assembly adopted the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families (resolution 45/158).

International Day of Family Remittances

In June 2018, the General Assembly proclaimed 16 June as the International Day of Family Remittances. The resolution proclaiming the day recognizes that remittances, including those sent by migrants, are essential for all Sustainable

Development Goals and long-term development strategies, in particular poverty reduction.

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